

DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OYO TOWN, OYO STATE, NIGERIA: THE ROLE OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

Abstract:

This paper examines the role of mathematics education in the development of entrepreneurial skills among secondary school students. The population of the study was 650 SSS3 students from fifteen (15) public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. The technique used to select three (3) Secondary Schools was simple Random Sampling. All the students in the three (3) selected schools, making a total of One Hundred and Ninety-Five (195) SSS3 students were used as sample for the study. Three (3) research questions guided the study. The collection of data was done using self-constructed 21-item student questionnaires (SQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.84 and analysed using Mean and Standard deviation for the research questions. The findings of the study among others indicated that; Mathematic education plays a significant role in the development of entrepreneurial skills among SSS3 students, mathematical knowledge provides entrepreneurial skills acquisition, male and female student responses on the need of mathematical knowledge for entrepreneurial skills acquisition do not significantly differ. Against this background, it was recommended that; strategies should be put in place by government to intimate mathematics teachers at all level of educational systems of the role of mathematics education in the development of entrepreneurial skills among SSS3 students; qualified teachers should be employed to teach school mathematics that will boost students' mathematics knowledge and thereby bring about improvement in Nigeria economy among others.

Keywords:

Mathematics Education, Entrepreneurship Skills, Development.

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Introduction

Nigeria, like the majority of developing countries worldwide, is beset by a multitude of issues and harsh realities, such as poverty, unemployment, violence, and illness (Oviawe, 2020). These circumstances pose serious threats to people's ability to survive in the majority of developing countries, which makes it necessary to teach educated men and women who can contribute positively to their communities. The imbalance between the demands of the labor market and the graduates' lack of critical marketable skills is the cause of the high rate of unemployment among Nigerian graduates from various higher education institutions (Diejomal & Okimolade, 2015, Dabelen, Oni & Adekola, 2010). The current skill gaps impede youth growth, which in turn impedes the development of the country. Educating students in entrepreneurship may be able to stop this negative tendency. As a result, it has become increasingly important to teach students how to be self-reliant, and Nigerians have been demanding this for a long time. Nigeria developed vision 2020, which aims to place the country among the top 20 economies in the world, in order to fulfill this aspiration. Entrepreneurship education is required to accomplish this goal.

Entrepreneurship education is that branch of information that gives someone the mentality to apply the skills and knowledge they have learned in school to take the risk of trying something new. Students who have an education in entrepreneurship develop the abilities needed to be independent. These abilities include, but are not limited to, resilience, focus, creativity, problem-solving, focus, resource management, goal-setting, and decision-making. According to Venkataraman (2020), entrepreneurship is any action that entails identifying, assessing, and seizing chances to launch new products and services, as well as new markets, procedures, raw materials, and methods of organization by organizing activities that had not been released before. Thus, the process of creating, establishing, and managing a new company, such as a Start-up Company that provides a product, process, or service, has been the traditional definition of entrepreneurship. Additionally, entrepreneurship is defined as the process of putting in the required time and effort to create something unique and valuable, taking on the associated financial, psychological, and social risk, and reaping the financial and personal rewards that follow (Ibe, 2023). Innovation, opportunity recognition, process, and expansion in business and employment strategy management practices are characteristics of entrepreneurs (Watson, 2016). According to Rwigema and Venter (2015), innovation is the process of developing new and improved commercialized methods of completing tasks. Mathematics is a key component of this kind of instruction.

Since everyone needs mathematics, it is the doorway and secret to building entrepreneurship abilities (Aasa & Sabitu, 2023). As a result, pupils who are ready for self-sustenance in life will benefit from the realization of the aforementioned needs for mathematics. The science of mathematics examines the logic of amount, shape, and order. There is mathematics everywhere, and it affects everything we do. Onyeachu (2016) asserts that mathematics serves as a model for reasoning, creating scientific scenarios, coming to conclusions, and resolving issues in practical settings. There is a positive correlation between problem solving and entrepreneurship education, according to a small number of research (Uka, 2015). Thus, just as creativity is a component of entrepreneurship, problem solving is a component of mathematics itself. Therefore, there are relationships among the variables.

Everything in life involves mathematics (Eze, 2019). There are numerous chances for students to apply mathematics in almost every field they may choose to study as well as in many aspects of daily life. Our creative and critical thinking are enhanced by mathematics. Adewumi and Adu (2021) conjectured that mathematics is composed of two dimensions, which makes sense.

1. **Mathematical Understanding:** This is the understanding of what functions and what can be created.
2. **Mathematical Techniques and Skills:** These involve applying this knowledge to everyday instruments and processes.

3. Because of its practical use, Hassan (2015) contended that mathematics is now widely acknowledged as a topic that is essential to the economic independence and long-term growth of any country. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), secondary education focuses on two main areas: (i) preparing students for productive lives in society, and (ii) preparing them for higher education. To be more precise, secondary schools ought to:
 - a) Diversify their curricula to accommodate students' varying abilities, opportunities, and roles that arise during or after their secondary school education.
 - b) Give pupils the tools they need to survive in the scientific and technological society we live in.
 - c) Raise a generation of individuals who can think independently, respect other people's opinions and feelings, uphold the dignity of labor, and recognize the ideals outlined in our overarching national goals in order to live moral lives.
 - d) Encourage students to aspire to success and self-improvement in the classroom and in the future.

Since mathematics is essential to all aspects of life, it has been required as a core subject. The goal of mathematical education is to eradicate poverty, create jobs, reorient values, and generate wealth. These are the main goals of mathematics curricula. These goals are admirable and, if carefully planned and carried out, research projects like the one described in this paper can help the country thrive. Thus, among other things, the general goals of mathematics education are to:

- Create a passion for mathematics and offer a strong basis for daily life.
- To cultivate the motivation and capacity to be correct to the extent that it is pertinent to the issue at hand; • To enhance computational skills
- To cultivate exact, rational, and abstract thought

Developing the capacity to identify issues and apply relevant mathematical knowledge to solve them; supplying the basis in mathematics required for additional education; and fostering and stimulating creativity.

Thus, it is evident that the goals of mathematics instruction align with the overall goals of education. Therefore, if pupils are not taught entrepreneurship to become self-reliant, these stated goals cannot be met. Since entrepreneurship is all about invention and creativity, mathematics is important to its growth (Udosa, 2015).

Nigeria is undoubtedly endowed with a wealth of natural resources. Nigeria's economy has not considerably responded to the pressures of demand from over one hundred and eighty million people, despite the country's abundance of natural resources and the enormous wealth earned by the sale of oil and gas. This shows that wealth cannot last forever in the absence of a thriving manufacturing sector. Industry observers predict that as more nations decide to outlaw gasoline-powered vehicles, Nigeria's economy, which is mostly reliant on the sale of crude oil on the global market, may be doomed. Thus, it is necessary to look ahead to a Nigeria where its people can be independent and self-employed and where the country is not just dependent on oil and gas. Based on this context, the purpose of this paper is to ascertain whether mathematical knowledge can help students acquire entrepreneurial talents like innovation and problem-solving abilities.

Statement of the Problem

Economic instability and unemployment are global problems that do not only affect Nigeria. Nations have implemented several strategies to mitigate the threat; yet, the issue continues to exist. It has been determined that entrepreneurship, which calls for skill development, is a way to help students become self-sufficient and capable of helping their fellow citizens find opportunities and go on to create new economic activities by starting new businesses. These are abilities that must be developed, and

developing them requires a sufficient understanding of mathematics. Therefore, the study's problem statement is as follows: "Is the role of mathematics education capable of boosting SSS 3 students' acquisition of entrepreneurial skills? Stated differently, how much does a student's learning of entrepreneurial skills depend on their understanding of mathematics education?"

Purpose of the Study

This study's primary goal is to determine how mathematics instruction contributes to secondary school students' growth as entrepreneurs. The study specifically aims to ascertain the following:

1. The degree to which secondary school pupils' development of entrepreneurial skills is influenced by their education in mathematics.
2. The degree to which learning mathematics fosters the development of entrepreneurial skills.
3. The average answers from male and female students on the necessity of mathematics understanding for learning entrepreneurial skills.

Research Questions

To direct the investigation, the following research questions were posed.

1. How much of a role does mathematics education have in helping secondary school students improve their entrepreneurial skills?
2. How much can knowledge of mathematics aid in the development of entrepreneurial skills?
3. What is the average reaction from students, both male and female, regarding the necessity of mathematics knowledge for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills?

Methodology

Since the study's respondents' opinions were gathered in the field, a survey research design was chosen. The study, which was conducted in Oyo State's Oyo East Local Government Area, focused on how mathematics education helps students in Senior Secondary Schools 3 enhance their entrepreneurial skills. All SSS 3 math students enrolled in public secondary schools in Oyo State's Oyo East Local Government Area make up the study's population. 195 Senior Secondary School Three (SSS3) students make up the study's sample. The sample size, which consists of three (3) complete classes from the fifteen (15) public secondary schools in the Local Government Area under study, was chosen using a simple random sampling procedure. A self-structured questionnaire was the tool utilized to obtain the data. A modified Likert response scale with four points—Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)—was given to the respondents to express their opinions. The weights of the items ranged from 4 to 1 for positively cued items and vice versa for negatively cued items. The Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo's measurement and evaluation, mathematics, and entrepreneurship experts verified the instruments and certified their suitability for the study. For reliability, twenty (20) copies of the instrument were given to Afijio Local Government students who are not involved in the research project. Test-retest methodology yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84.

Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data that were gathered.

Results

The results of the study were obtained from research questions answered through data collected and analysed. Any item with mean score of 2.50 and above was adjudged accepted, while items with mean score below 2.50 is adjudged rejected. The tables below shows the summary of the results of the data collected.

Research Question 1: To what extent do mathematics education play significant role in the development of entrepreneurial skills among secondary school students?

Table 1: Mean Responses of the Significant Roles Mathematics Education Play in the Development of Entrepreneurial Skills among SSS 3 Students.

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	SD	DECISION
1	Most successful entrepreneurs are god at Mathematics	3.20	1.79	Accepted
2	Mathematics teachers who teach well can be good entrepreneurs	3.00	1.73	Accepted
3	An entrepreneur should be able to compute discount with the knowledge of Mathematics	2.89	1.64	Accepted
4	Acquisition of entrepreneurial skills need adequate knowledge of Mathematics	3.90	1.70	Accepted
5	The knowledge of Mathematics will help an entrepreneur to calculate unit and total cost of articles sold	3.10	1.76	Accepted
6	An entrepreneur needs to have the knowledge of Mathematics to be able to plan and coordinate business activities effectively and efficiently	3.00	1.73	Accepted
7	Students who do well in Mathematics can be good entrepreneur	3.80	1.95	Accepted

The results in the table 1 above shows that the mean scores of all items fall above the benchmark of 2.50 and so, all items were accepted. Hence, the result shows that mathematics education play significant role in the development of entrepreneurial skills among SSS 3 students.

Research Question 2: To what extent do mathematics knowledge provides entrepreneurial skills acquisition?

Table 2: Mean Responses on how Mathematics Education provides Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition.

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	SD	DECISION
8	Knowledge of basic Mathematics operation (+, -, x, ÷) cannot provide growth in Business	1.60	1.26	Rejected
9	Mathematics knowledge helps students to think of how to start their business after SSS 3 especially those who could not further their education	3.10	1.97	Accepted
10	With the help of Mathematics knowledge entrepreneurs are able to develop market survey to sell their product	3.04	1.92	Accepted
11	Students have understood that Mathematical knowledge can help an entrepreneur to analyse gains and loss in the business	3.25	1.98	Accepted

12	The knowledge of Mathematics helps students to reconcile check and balance account for business owners	3.42	2.06	Accepted
13	The knowledge of Mathematics will help students to see the link between Mathematics and business	3.10	1.76	Accepted
14	The knowledge of Mathematics education helps students to understand that Mathematics does not entail calculations only, but can be applied to other areas of Life pursuit especially in entrepreneurship education	3.16	1.72	Accepted

Table 2 above shows the extent Mathematics knowledge provides entrepreneurial skills acquisition. From the table, the mean scores of items 9 – 14 are above the benchmark of 2.50 and were accepted, except for item 8 whose mean score was below the benchmark of 2.50 and was rejected. This means that the knowledge of basic Mathematics operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division are needed in entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

Research Question 3: What is the mean response of male and female students on the needs of mathematical knowledge in entrepreneurial skills acquisition?

Table 3: Mean Responses on the extent to which Mathematical Skills enhances Entrepreneurial Skills

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	SD	DECISION
15	An entrepreneur with average Mathematical skills can manage his business efficiently	3.18	1.92	Accepted
16	Those who are Mathematically inclined are innovative when it comes to entrepreneur activities	4.32	2.08	Accepted
17	Entrepreneur with good knowledge of mathematics perform better than their counterparts who are not good in Mathematics	4.20	2.05	Accepted
18	Mathematical skills acquisition brings about creativity in entrepreneurial activities.	3.60	1.90	Accepted
19	The knowledge of Mathematics helps an entrepreneur to solve problems faster than his contemporaries	3.80	1.94	Accepted
20	The use of Mathematical skills can lead to acquisition of creative entrepreneurial skills	3.35	1.82	Accepted
21	A good knowledge of Mathematics brings about innovations in entrepreneurial activities	3.60	1.90	Accepted

The results in table three above shows the extent to which mathematical skills enhances innovation and creativity in entrepreneurial skills. The mean scores of items 15 – 21 are all above the benchmark of 2.50. Hence, all the items were accepted. This indicates that mathematical skills are a booster to entrepreneurial skills.

Discussion of the Findings

Based on the data analysis shown in Table 1, it can be concluded that SSS 3 students' development of entrepreneurial abilities is significantly influenced by their mathematical education. This is consistent with research by Uka (2015), who claimed that strong entrepreneurial skill development results from efficient mathematics teaching and learning.

The data analysis shown in Table 2 indicates that learning mathematics facilitates the development of entrepreneurial skills. This is consistent with the observation made by Eukoha (2022) that almost no field of scientific or entrepreneurship education does not employ mathematical ideas to describe its own ideas, hypotheses, or models.

According to the data analysis shown in Table 3, having a mathematical background improves an entrepreneur's capacity for creativity and invention. This is in line with Effiom's (2020) observation that increased scientific understanding and the use of contemporary technologies in mathematics education will undoubtedly boost economic viability and production.

Conclusion

For secondary school pupils to develop entrepreneurial abilities, they need a strong foundation in mathematics. One component that is crucial to the development of entrepreneurial education—which the nation is yearning for—is mathematics. Self-reliance, self-sufficiency, and self-actualization are prerequisites for these goals. This is a result of Nigeria's economy, which is the biggest in Africa and the 22nd largest in the world, continuing to be mostly dependent on crude oil for survival. According to Oviawe (2020), Nigerian kids who receive entrepreneurship education that is well-planned and carried out would grow into devoted and successful workers or employers. In other words, if more graduates choose to start their own businesses, Nigeria's economy will undoubtedly grow significantly and this will help ensure that the country will have more to offer than only oil and gas in the future.

Recommendations

The recommendations listed below are based on the findings discussed and the outcomes shown above:

- The government ought to implement certain measures to inform math teachers at all educational levels about the contribution of mathematics education to the growth of secondary school students' entrepreneurial abilities.
- Employing qualified math teachers to teach math in schools will increase students' mathematical understanding and foster the development of entrepreneurial abilities, which will benefit Nigeria's economy.
- At all educational levels in Nigeria, mathematics instruction—an essential component of entrepreneurship education—should be promoted and reinforced.
- The government ought to provide developing entrepreneurial talents sufficient consideration and assistance.
- Mathematics teachers should work to instill confidence in their pupils and motivate them to see the connection between learning mathematics and entrepreneurship as beneficial.

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